

TESTING OF SANDWICH STRUCTURES WITH CFRP SKINS IN EDGEWISE COMPRESSION

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Keywords: *Composite, Sandwich, Crushing, Energy Absorption, Testing*

1 Introduction

The automotive industry has to address increasingly stringent CO₂ emissions targets as well as increasing fuel cost. In general reduction of CO₂ emissions may be achieved by reducing the overall weight of the vehicle. Battery electric (BEV) and range extender vehicles (REX) may be other options to reduce overall emissions and improve sustainability but they are typically associated with additional weight, for example due to the weight of the batteries or additional components. As an example for a BEV vehicle the Tesla Model S has a curb weight of 2110kg [1], while a comparable combustion engine vehicle, such as the BMW 6series, has a curb weight of 1760kg [2].

In addition, customer expectations and safety requirements are continuously increasing, mostly leading to an increase in vehicle weight to meet novel safety requirements [3]. In conclusion, existing materials and vehicle architectures will mostly result in increasing weight, which may alleviate the possible emission reductions for BEV and REX vehicles.

One option to reduce vehicle weight, which will be explored here, is the use of novel materials to improve passive safety of vehicles. In most side impact events the side frame, supported by the under floor and some additional struts, such as the seat cross members, will resist the intrusion into the passenger compartment to protect the occupants. By using novel sandwich materials with carbon fibre reinforced plastic (CFRP) face sheets the supporting structure may be stiffer and more suited to absorb and distribute the impact energy, which may improve crash performance and allow reductions of overall vehicle weight.

In-plane crushing of sandwich structures has been investigated by Mamalis et. al. [4] using four

different core materials and two different glass fibre reinforced face sheets to produce eight specimens. The specimens were tested in an unsupported configuration in edgewise compression and it was found that the mechanical properties of the core greatly influenced the failure of the structure and thus their energy absorption. The authors observed three general collapse modes:

- Mode I, unstable sandwich column buckling with foam core shear failure,
- Mode II, unstable sandwich disintegration with buckling of faceplates to opposite directions, and
- Mode III, progressive end-crushing of the sandwich panels.

The sandwich panels collapsing in Mode III reached the highest specific energy absorption (SEA) values. Similar results were reported by Stapleton and Adams [5] using balsa wood and polyurethane foam as core material and CFRP face sheets. The authors observed that specimens failing in Mode III had the highest energy absorption; however this did not in general occur for specimens with the highest core strength or stiffness. Rather, the stable collapse of the face-sheets was found to be the main driver for high energy absorption. To confirm this, Stapleton and Adams [6] conducted a second study where the face sheet to core interface was reinforced, for example using stitching. In all cases the specimens with an enhanced interface yielded higher energy absorption.

Assuming stable Mode III collapse occurs, Velecela, Found and Soutis [7] demonstrated that the thickness of the face sheets largely governed energy absorption provided that buckling was prevented. Such test configurations, where the specimen sides are supported have first been proposed by Lavoie and coworkers [8,9] and have been adopted by other

researchers to study the energy absorption of flat specimens [10]. However, as argued by Feraboli [11] testing specimens in a fully supported configuration may yield inaccurate results since the crush failure front cannot be freely established. The aim of this work is thus twofold. First the introduction of a novel test rig for testing flat plates and sandwiches during dynamic impact with possible crush failure in different modes. Secondly, to study the energy absorption of several sandwich systems with carbon fibre face sheets during static and dynamic impact.

2 Experimental procedures

2.1 Test rig development

The sandwich specimens were tested on a drop weight test rig. To improve the sample alignment and prevent buckling a special test rig was developed that would improve sample alignment and allow a more accurate recording of the crushing force at the impactor, see Fig. 1 and Fig. 2. Most test setups use a stationary specimen on a flat plate which is supported at the sides using guides. The specimen is then compressed by a flat impactor. However, this results in a continuously changing crash front location, which is also constrained at the sides through the guides. The first makes it difficult to study failure events in detail since the entire test area has to be captured, for example using high-speed cameras. The second results in significant suppression of the delamination failure between the skins and core often observed for sandwiches in edgewise compression. This in turn may yield inaccurate data for designing actual components, since the sandwich component may not necessarily be constrained.

The proposed setup therefore has a moving specimen and a fixed impact plate that the specimen is dropped onto. The rig was designed to allow testing of specimens of 70 x 70mm up to 120 x 300mm and a maximum thickness of 50mm. The specimen is clamped at the top using a base plate, which was connected with a load cell. To distribute the reaction force at the clamp side over the entire specimen surface including the skins, sliding wedges are used that are mounted into the clamp together with the specimen.

During testing the specimen falls freely into the alignment guides, which are semicircles on four sides. A flattened section at the top allows the sample to fall into the guides without undue friction. The specimen is then impacted against a flat plate and deforms freely over an unsupported length, which can be adjusted using different alignment sections.

Fig 1: Digital rendering of the sandwich crushing test rig.

Fig 2: Image of the test rig integrated into the Impact Tower.

To modify the test further, other impact plates may be included, for example wedges or similar. For this work the unsupported length was 25mm in all cases. The crush plate, which is a flat plate here, can be exchanged for a three-component load cell, which can be mounted through a hole under the crush plate. A potential problem for this inverted test configuration however, is the fact that the debris of the deformed specimen accumulates at the impact zone. To mitigate this effect an extraction system may also be employed.

2.2 Specimen Configuration and Manufacture

The test specimens used in this research all had carbon fibre weave face sheets consisting of three plies with a 0/90 fibre orientation each and a nominal thickness of 0.2mm. The plies were aligned with the edges of the sandwich core, to ensure that the extraction orientation of the specimens did not affect the mechanical properties of the skins. Specimens were manufactured in a closed mould by impregnating the dry top and bottom face sheets, which were then placed in the mould together with the core material and pressed at elevated pressure. The injection resin was Momentive L1100 with an Epikure 294 curing agent. They were then tempered at 70°C for two hours to ensure a uniform degree of cure.

In total 13 different core materials were used to manufacture test plates of 400x400mm, Table 1. In all cases the nominal core thickness was 10mm, and the total face sheet thickness was approximately 0.6mm for each side. A difference between the nominal specimen thickness of 11.2mm and the final thickness was found due to post-tempering after cure which resulted in shrinkage and expansion of the cores. For the Airex C 70 Material the last two numbers indicate the nominal density in kg/m³. This is also true for the PUR material, while for Rohacell the number in the name indicates the nominal material density, again measured in kg/m³.

2.3 Static Testing

Static tests were conducted to enable setting up the dynamic tests and to allow a comparison between the static and dynamic test data. The static test pieces were 70mm wide and 100mm long, Fig. 3. Velecela and Soutis [12] studied different trigger

configurations and concluded that from the investigated variations a triangular trigger with 14deg inclination was most effective at reducing peak loads and was consequently used here. From each sandwich plate three specimens were extracted including the triangular trigger for quasi-static testing using a circular saw. After manufacture and milling the specimen dimensions were recorded using a calliper and the samples were weighed to later calculate the specific energy absorption (SEA).

Table 1: Overview of Core Materials

Core Material	Density [kg/m ³]
AIREX C 70.40	40
AIREX C 70.55	60
AIREX C 70.75	80
AIREX C 70.90	100
AIREX T 92.80	85
AIREX T 92.100	105
PUR RG 60	60
ROHACELL 31 IG-F	32
ROHACELL 51 IG-F	52
ROHACELL 71 IG-F	75
ROHACELL 110 IG-F	110
AMORIM CoreCork NL10	120
BALTEK Balsawood SB 100	153

Fig 3: Static test specimen dimensions.

The test-rig shown in Figs. 1 and 2 was adapted for a servo-hydraulic press. This was done by producing inserts to guide the smaller 70mm wide specimens. Specimens were tested at a constant displacement rate of $v = 0.0055$ m/s and a total displacement of 50mm, Fig. 4. The average of three specimens was taken for the SEA and mean load. Pictures were taken of the specimens before and after testing.

2.4 Dynamic Testing

Dynamic impact specimens were comparable to the static specimens but had a length of 300mm and a width of 120mm, Fig. 5, with the same 14deg triangular trigger that was used previously for the static specimens. The extended length was due to a minimum mass and test speed that could be used in the drop tower, which meant that a minimum energy absorption was necessary for all specimens.

Fig. 4: Airex C70.90 specimen undergoing quasi-static testing.

Specimens were again machined from the total sandwich plate using CNC milling. The sandwich specimens were tested on an impact tower using a drop weight with a mass of 17.4kg and an impact velocity between 5m/s and 8.2 m/s, Fig. 6. The impact velocity was based upon the results of quasi-static validation experiments to ensure a reasonable crash length.

For dynamic testing the sample clamp was adapted with two sliding wedges that were mounted into the clamp, together with the specimen to ensure a consistent application of force over the complete cross section. The specimen was mounted at the top of the impactor. During testing guides were adjusted to allow the specimen to fall freely through the

guides and onto the crush platen. The guide rails ended 25mm ahead of the crush platen, to enable the specimen to deform freely. The travel of the impactor was recorded using laser positioning.

Fig. 5: Dynamic test specimen dimensions

Fig. 6. Test setup for dynamic testing

To calculate the effective load the acceleration was recorded and calculated into an effective impact force using the known mass of the impactor and specimen. Before and after testing images of the specimens were taken to document specific failure events. During testing a high-speed camera was used to monitor the cross-section of the sandwich specimens and to enable subsequent analysis of the failure events during crushing.

3 Experimental results

3.1 Static testing

For the static test results the recorded load was calculated into a specific energy absorption using the effective crushed material, Eq. 1.

$$SEA = \frac{W}{\rho A \delta} = \int_0^{\delta} F d\delta \rho A \delta \quad (1)$$

where W is the total absorbed energy, ρ is the density of the material, A the cross-section, δ the total crush displacement and F the Crush Force. The calculated results are given in Fig 7. To calculate the mean SEA the average of three specimens was taken. While this is by no means a significant number of test specimens it does provide an indication of the relative SEA, which was the main purpose of the static testing. Test number 31 for Rohacell 110 IG-F yielded a significantly higher load than the other two tests and this was attributed to the specimen having locked between the guiderails. The specimen was thus excluded from further analysis.

3.2 Dynamic testing

Dynamic test results were initially recalculated into force-displacement data using the measured acceleration, Eq. 2.

$$F = m * a \quad (2)$$

The SEA was then calculated using Eq. 1. An overview of the dynamic test results is given in Fig. 8. The SEA was again calculated as the average form three specimens.

Fig 7: Mean SEA for static crush testing for different core materials.

For the tests 49, 50 and 75 no SEA data are given, due wrongly recorded acceleration values. This also means that for Airex C70.90 no standard deviation can be given.

Fig. 8: Mean SEA for dynamic crush testing for different core materials.

4 Discussion

Comparing the static and dynamic test results in Fig. 7 and Fig. 8 it can be seen that the dynamic SEA is generally markedly lower than the static SEA. For Balsawood the static and dynamic SEA are comparable. In general the dynamic test data exhibit a lower standard deviation than the static test data. A possible explanation could be the higher crushed specimen length for the dynamic test case where individual failure events are averaged out, while they can be dominant for the short static crush length. Another possible explanation could be the change of failure mode between the static and dynamic test case.

For the same core material, SEA tends to increase with increasing density and this trend holds for both dynamic and static testing. An exception is the Rohacell 110 IG-F material, which exhibits a lower SEA than the Rohacell 71 IG-F. For similar core materials a strong correlation between increasing elastic core properties, such as compression strength with SEA can be observed, Table 3. However, the T92 materials exhibit SEA values significantly below C70 cores with comparable density and elastic properties.

Table 2 gives an overview of the observed failure modes during testing. It can be seen that almost all specimens failed in a mode III failure, with the exception of Airex T92. 80, 100 and Rohacell 31 IG-F core materials. This may explain the surprisingly low SEA for the Airex material in dynamic testing, considering their relatively high density.

This may be explained using the qualitative failure events during impact. Fig. 9 shows a comparison between a C70.90 and a T92.80 core material, where the first exhibits localized failure, while the second shows global bending. Mode III failure, where the specimen is destroyed and energy is likely absorbed through frictional effects and generating of new surfaces.

Similarly, extended delaminating of the CFRP face sheets yielded lower SEA values when compared to localized delaminating just ahead of the point of impact, Fig. 10. The C70.75 core material shows extended delamination at the interface between face-sheets and core, while the Cork NL10 core shows stable and localized core and face-sheet failure.

Table 2: Failure Modes during static and dynamic testing.

Core Material	Static Testing	Dynamic Testing
AIREX C 70.40	III	III
AIREX C 70.55	III	III
AIREX C 70.75	III	III
AIREX C 70.90	III	III
AIREX T 92.80	III	II, III
AIREX T 92.100	III	II, III
PUR RG 60	III	III
ROHACELL 31 IG-F	III	I, II
ROHACELL 51 IG-F	III	III
ROHACELL 71 IG-F	III	III
ROHACELL 110 IG-F	III	III
AMORIM CoreCork NL10	III	III
BALTEK Balsawood SB 100	III	III

Fig. 9: Comparison between typical failure for an Airex C70.90 (top) and T92.80 (bottom) core material

This stable localized failure, often referred to as “crinkling” of the face-sheets can absorb large amounts of energy, due to the high stiffness of the carbon fibre weave. Consequently, the absolute mechanical properties of the core material cannot be

Table 3: Overview of some elastic properties of the core materials.

Static Mechanical Property	Core Material											
	AIREX C 70.40	AIREX C 70.55	AIREX C 70.75	AIREX C 70.90	AIREX T 92.80	AIREX T 92.100	ROHACELL 31 IG-F	ROHACELL 51 IG-F	ROHACELL 71 IG-F	ROHACELL 110 IG-F	AMORIM CoreKork NL10	BALTEK Balsa-wood SB 100
Compression Modulus [MPa]	41	69	104	130	70	90	36	70	92	160	5	4005
Compression Strength [MPa]	0.45	0.90	1.45	2.00	1.00	1.40	0.40	0.90	1.50	3.00	0.30	12.90
Tensile Modulus [MPa]	28	45	66	84	90	110	36	70	92	160	n/a	3570
Tensile Strength [MPa]	0.70	1.30	2.00	2.70	1.90	2.30	1.00	1.90	2.80	3.50	0.60	13.20
Shear Modulus [MPa]	13	22	30	40	17	21	13	19	29	50	6	160
Shear Strength [MPa]	0.45	0.85	1.20	1.70	0.65	0.90	0.40	0.80	1.30	2.40	0.90	3.00
Shear Strain [%]	8	16	18	23	30	20	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a

used to design sandwich systems for energy absorption. It seems that the interface has a dominant effect on SEA.

Fig. 10: Comparison between typical failure for an Airex C70.75 (top) and Cork NL10 (bottom) core material.

5 Summary

Sandwich specimens with CFRP weave facesheets and different core materials were tested using a novel test rig. The test-rig proposed here has the advantage of having a free deformation length where failure can occur without constraints resulting in different failure modes. It was used to test specimens in static and dynamic compression. For Airex and Rohacell core materials energy absorption mostly increased with increasing density. Due to the unique test-configuration some specimens showed extended delaminations or global bending, resulting in low SEA values. From the data it could be observed that localized failure of the core and face-sheets resulted in higher energy absorption. Ongoing work is aimed at simulating sandwich systems during in-plane impact. Further work will be aimed at identifying the impact of face-sheets on SEA as well as studying the importance of the skin-core interface on SEA.

Acknowledgements

Specimens were supplied by Gaugler & Lutz and the support by Mr. Pressel is gratefully acknowledged. Further thanks are due to Mr. Felix Behnisch, Mr. Greissl and Mr. Palmer for conducting the tests and analyzing the test data.

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